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Relationship between Quality Assurance Indices and Academic Staff Job Performance in Colleges of Education Yobe State, Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the Relationship between Quality Assurance Indices and Academic Staff Job Performance in Colleges of Education Yobe State, Nigeria. The objectives of the study were to determine the; relationship between instructional supervision and academic staff job performance in Colleges of Education Yobe State, Nigeria, relationship between infrastructural facilities and academic staff job performance in Colleges of Education Yobe State, Nigeria, two research questions and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study employed correlational and survey research designs and the population of One thousand four hundred and twenty three (1,423) respondents were used. The sample size of the study consisted of two hundred and eighty six (286) using research advisor table. The instrument used for data collection was a self- developed questionnaire titled “Quality Assurance Indices and Academic Staff Job Performance Questionnaire (QAIASJPQ). The instrument was face validated by professionals in the field of Educational Administration and Planning, Measurement and evaluation. The reliability index of 0.75 was obtained using Cronbach’s Alpha method. Data collected were analysed using both descriptive statistic and inferential statistic mean, standard deviation and Pearson Product Moment Correlation. The findings of the study revealed that there was significant relationship between instructional supervision and academic staff job performance, there was significant relationship between infrastructural facilities and academic staff job performance, quality assurance was a significant variables for enhancing the educational quality and achieving institutional goals. It was recommended that quality assurance officers should be train in the area of instructional supervision as it was also found to be related to academic staff job performance. In conclusion quality assurance variables are the major determinants of academic staff job performance in Colleges of Education Yobe state Nigeria. This means that quality assurance is an important subject or factor in determining academic staff job performance in Colleges of Education Yobe State, Nigeria.

Keywords: Quality Assurance, Instructional supervision, Job performance

INTRODUCTION

The development of a nation depends on the education provided for its citizens. For this purpose, the Federal Ministry of Education (FME), in its strategic plan for the development of the education sector, has set up a veritable framework that will ensure that our national education system is placed on a pedestal of responsiveness, functionality, and global competitiveness. According to the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014), 'education is an instrument for national development; to this end, the formulation of ideas, their integration for national development, and the interaction of persons and ideas are all aspects of education, among others. Education in Nigeria Western, or formal, education was started in 1842 only at the primary level by the Christian missionaries, who managed the educational system according to their respective philosophies. The creation of states in Nigeria could be said to have been the genesis of the divergent educational system in Nigeria. Although the introduction of Western education in Nigeria by missionaries was mainly for two major reasons: spreading of Christianity and, of course, easy and convenient administration by the colonial masters. Therefore, the practice and standard of the educational system differ from one state to another. This necessitated the establishment of the Federal Inspectorate Service (FIS) in 1967, with the aim of maintaining, monitoring/supervising, and improving the educational standard in schools through frequent inspection of schools.

Between 1973 and 1988, FIS was relatively autonomous, and the period witnessed its functions being well funded. However, with the 1988 Civil Service Reforms, FIS was made a department in FME. This situation was followed by dwindling budgetary allocations and delayed releases of funds, which led to the crippling of inspectorate activities and, consequently, the degeneration of the quality of the nation's education system. It is important to note that the inspection practices in Nigeria have, for a long time, remained those inherited from "Her Majesty's inspector." This justified the assertion that colonial administration convenience was one of the reasons for the introduction of Western education in Nigeria.

To arrest the situation, the Minister of Education recommended the adoption of a Quality Assurance (QA) approach to inspection in Nigeria during the 54th session of the National Council on Education (NCE) in Katsina, 2007. The session approved the QA approach and the restructuring and strengthening of federal and state inspectorates and local government supervisory offices for enhanced and sustainable quality assurance in education nationwide. In response, FIS adopted the quality assurance approach to inspection. Education Quality Assurance (EQA) is the process of collecting, analysing and utilizing education information in order to ensure that the pre-determined national standards are achieved optimally. According to the National Policy on Education (2004); "education is an instrument for national development as well as a tool for the formulation of ideas". Education in Nigeria, Western or formal education started in Nigeria in 1842 only at the primary level by the Christian missionaries who managed the educational system according to their respective philosophies".

The Federal Government maintains its legislative responsibility, as provided for in the Federal Republic of Nigeria in 2014, to set minimum standards and maintain quality assurance of education at all levels. These responsibilities constitute the main thrust for Education Quality Assurance by the Federal Government in collaboration with the state and their local governments as well as the private sector providers. The new strategic aim of EQA is to set and maintain quality standards and to ensure that the inputs, processes, and outputs of the education system meet the set standards. Consequently, the scope of education quality assurance is more than that of school inspection. Education quality assurance involves, in serious ways, the processes of monitoring, assessing, evaluating, and quality controlling (remediation, counseling, supervision, and maintenance of resources, etc.). It also involves accreditation of the education system and communication of judgments obtained to all concerned in order to ensure quality with integrity, public accountability, and consistent improvement. The features of an effective quality assurance system are: Effective quality management system; Periodic audit of the operation of the system; and Periodic review of the National External Quality Assurance Programme (NEQAP) below tertiary.

Supervision as a field of education is as old as formal education. Supervision is a management tool for secondary school principals. Instructional supervision facilitates teachers' improvement in instructional

practices. With quality and relevant instruction of students, the academic achievement of students is assured. Supervision began in USA as a process of external inspection. At this period one or more local citizens were appointed to inspect what the teachers were teaching. Superintendents were later appointed to inspect schools to see that teachers were following the prescribed curriculum and see that students were able to recite their lessons.

Supervision is as old as the school system. Supervision has undergone series of evolution since the colonial era. It is directed towards sustaining teaching and learning process in the educational system. According to Ogba and Igu (2014) supervision has been identified as one of the approaches to teacher effectiveness. Supervision according to Modebelu (2018) is a process of assisting, directing, stimulating and motivating teachers to enhance teaching and learning process in educational institution. Ogbo (2015), defined supervision as the maximum development of the teacher into the most professionally efficient and effective person he is capable of becoming. According to Modebelu (2018), is a process of assisting, directing, stimulating, and motivating teachers to enhance the teaching and learning process in educational institutions.

Infrastructural facilities are the physical things that facilitate teaching and learning in schools. It includes the laboratories, libraries, workshops, classrooms, and equipment. Infrastructures Among such concepts are the “school plant”, “learning resources”, “physical resources”, and “educational resources”, to mention but a few. Subair (2015) described infrastructure as the operational inputs of every instructional program and constitutive elements that are necessary for teaching and learning. Such include buildings, laboratories, machinery, furniture, and electrical fixtures.

Dare (2014), define infrastructural facilities as all the available assets of a school that can be used to foster and facilitate effective teaching and learning as well as to protect the physical well-being of the occupants? This implies that no educational programme can function effectively without the provision of infrastructural facilities such as: good buildings (comfortable classrooms), good roads (accessibility), technology (computer), water supply, power supply, (supply of foods) etc., With the provision of the above infrastructural facilities, educational programmes like formal, informal and non-formal can function as expected (Oyedeji, 2012). Aside the fact that, infrastructural facilities are the material things that facilitate teaching and learning processes in schools, the duo concepts of teaching and learning are opposite sides of a coin, for a lesson is not taught until it has been learned. This is in addition to the fact that the importance of teaching and learning on the provision of adequate instructional facilities for education cannot be over-emphasized. The dictum had been “teaching is inseparable from learning while learning is separable from teaching”. In Colleges of Education, these facilities include administrative and classroom blocks and libraries, residential facilities (dormitory, staff quarters, dinning and comprene halls, security- post, store, toilet facilities, water and power supplies etc.), and recreational facilities (football, handball, volley ball, hockey field and other field events, lawn/table tennis, net ball, racket ball and basketball courts etc.). These facilities are designed to support the process of teaching and learning in schools.

Statement of the Problem

The researcher observed while discussing with members of Academic Staff Union of Colleges of Education in Yobe State Nigeria that the quality of teacher education programs is gradually declaying and not as expected and this may be as a results of inadequate instructional supervision and inadequate infrastructural facilities, in our Colleges of Education in Yobe State, Nigeria. It is against this background that the study determined the instructional supervision, infrastructural facilities and Academic Staff Job Performance in Colleges of Education in Yobe State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study were to determine the relationship between:

- 1 Instructional supervision and academic staff job performance in Colleges of Education in Yobe State, Nigeria;

2 Infrastructural facilities and academic staff job performance in Colleges of Education in Yobe State, Nigeria;

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

- H₀₁:** There is no significant relationship between instructional supervision and academic staff job performance in Colleges of Education in Yobe State, Nigeria;
- H₀₂:** There is no significant relationship between infrastructural facilities and academic staff job performance in Colleges of Education in Yobe State, Nigeria;

METHODOLOGY

The study employed correlational and survey research designs and the population of One thousand four hundred and twenty three (1,423) respondents were used. The sample size of the study consisted of two hundred and eight six (286) using research advisor table. The instrument used for data collection was a self- developed questionnaire titled “Quality Assurance Indices and Academic Staff Job Performance Questionnaire (QAIASJPQ). The instrument was face validated by professionals in the field of Educational Administration and Planning, Measurement and evaluation. The reliability index of 0.75 was obtained using Cronbach’s Alpha method. Data collected were analysed using both descriptive statistic and inferential statistic mean, standard deviation and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was used to test the two hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between instructional supervision and academic staff job performance in Colleges of Education in Yobe State, Nigeria.

Table 4.1: Correlation Coefficient Relationship between Instructional Supervision and Academic Staff Job Performance in Colleges of Education in Yobe State, Nigeria

Variables	N	df	Mean	r	P-value	Decision
Instructional Supervision	286	284	21.0271	.536	.000	Rejected
Academic Performance	286	284	21.3527			

Significance at 0.05 2 tailed

Table 1 shows the relationship between instructional supervision and academic staff job performance in Colleges of Education in Yobe State, Nigeria. The r - value is .536, and the p - value of .000, which is less than .05. Hence, the hypothesis is rejected, this indicates that, there is significant correlation between instructional supervision and academic staff job performance in College of Education in Yobe State, Nigeria. This suggested that effective instructional supervision is a major determinant of the personnel’ job performance.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between infrastructural facilities and academic staff job performance in Colleges of Education in Yobe State, Nigeria.

Table 4.2: Correlation Coefficient Relationship between Infrastructural Facilities and Academic Staff Job Performance in Colleges of Education in Yobe State, Nigeria

Variables	N	df	Mean	r	P-value	Decision
Infrastructural Facilities	286	284	18.5659	.398	.000	Rejected
Academic Performance	286	284	21.3527			

Significance at 0.05 2 tailed

The Table 2 reveals the relationship between infrastructural facilities and academic staff job performance in Colleges of Education in Yobe State, Nigeria. The r - value is .398, and the p - value of .000, which is

less than .05. Hence, the hypothesis is rejected, this shows that there is significant correlation between infrastructural facilities and academic staff job performance in College of Education in Yobe State, Nigeria. This suggests that improved infrastructural facilities are associated with better academic staff job performance.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Hypothesis one determined the relationship between instructional supervision and academic staff job performance in Colleges of Education in Yobe State, Nigeria. The study revealed a significant correlation between instructional supervision and academic staff job performance in Colleges of Education in Yobe State, Nigeria. A study conducted by Dauda, Bawa, Umar, and Bala (2018) carried out a study on the influence of instructional supervision on teachers' performance in technical colleges of Yobe State, Nigeria. Findings of the study revealed, among others, that internal instructional supervision is being carried out, and it significantly improves teacher job performance in technical colleges of Yobe State. The finding of this current study is also in agreement with Dauda *et al.*'s finding, which revealed that there is a significant relationship between instructional supervision and academic staff job performance in Colleges of Education in Yobe State, Nigeria. Furthermore, Danasabe (2018) conducted a study on principals' instructional supervision and teachers' performance of secondary schools in the Danko Wasagu Local Government Area of Kebbi State, Northwest Nigeria. The findings of the study indicated that principals' instructional supervision had an overall mean of 2.78, which indicates that principals of the secondary school perform their instructional supervision, and the findings of the study on teachers' performance indicated an overall mean of 2.57, which implies that teachers perform their school responsibilities. This is also in agreement with the current finding, which also revealed a significant relationship between instructional supervision and academic staff job performance in Colleges of Education in Yobe State, Nigeria. Although the scope of the study differs, the finding of the study revealed the same.

Hypothesis two determined the relationship between infrastructural facilities and academic staff job performance in Colleges of Education in Yobe State, Nigeria. The finding revealed a significant relationship between infrastructural facilities and academic staff job performance in Colleges of Education in Yobe State, Nigeria. In a study conducted by Folasade and Afolakemi (2021), the researchers investigated the influence of tertiary institution infrastructural facilities on lecturers' job satisfaction and performance in Ibadan Metropolis, Oyo State, Nigeria. The study revealed that infrastructural facilities have significant combined influence on lecturers' job satisfaction and performance in both public and private tertiary institutions in the Ibadan metropolis of Oyo State, Nigeria. This finding is in agreement with the finding of this study, which also revealed a significant relationship between infrastructural facilities and academic staff job performance in Colleges of Education in Yobe State, Nigeria. Okoroma and Orike (2019) investigated the influence of infrastructural facilities on the academic performance of undergraduate students of federal universities in the South-South Zone, Nigeria. The result showed that the respondents unanimously agree that infrastructural facilities in university education influence the academic performance of undergraduate students of Federal Universities in the South-South Zone, Nigeria. The finding of Okoroma and Orike further vindicates the finding of this study, which also revealed a significant relationship between infrastructural facilities and academic staff job performance in Colleges of Education in Yobe State, Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

Quality assurance indices are the major determinants of academic staff job performance in Yobe Education Zone, Yobe State, Nigeria. This means that quality assurance is an important subject or factor in determining academic staff job performance in Yobe Education Zone, Yobe State, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made to improve quality assurance mechanisms and enhance academic staff job performance in Colleges of Education in Yobe State, Nigeria:

1. Institutionalize Robust Instructional Supervision Practices: The Federal Ministry of Education and the NCCE should develop and enforce a standardised framework for instructional supervision across all Colleges of Education. Supervisory visits should be more frequent, participatory, and developmental rather than punitive.
2. Invest Heavily in Infrastructure Development: Government agencies (e.g., TETFund, NCCE) should increase budgetary allocations for infrastructural development in colleges. Modern teaching facilities, well equipped laboratories, libraries, internet access, and conducive office spaces should be prioritized to support staff productivity and student learning.

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